

A Simple Preparation of Comenaldehyde Methyl Ether

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The direct oxidation of kojic acid derivatives to aldehydes containing the 4*H*-pyran-4-one nucleus has been the subject of recent interest. Earlier attempts to obtain comenaldehyde (IV) were all unsuccessful^{1,2}. Since our work was completed, the successful preparations of comenaldehyde methyl ether^{3,4} (V) and comenaldehyde benzyl ether (VI)⁵ have been reported. All these methods involve the use of manganese dioxide for the oxidation of the hydroxymethyl group in compounds (II) and (III). In view of the tedious preparation of the active manganese dioxide⁶, the usefulness of this reaction as a preparative method, particularly on a large scale, is somewhat impaired.

(I): R=H; R'=CH₂OH. (II): R=Me; R'=CH₂OH.
 (III): R=CH₂Ph; R'=CH₂OH. (IV): R=H; R'=CHO.
 (V): R=Me; R'=CHO. (VI): R=CH₂Ph; R'=CHO.

We record here an easy laboratory method in which commercial selenium dioxide without purification has been found to perform the oxidation quite satisfactorily. This has considerably simplified the preparation of the methyl ether (V), affording good yields in less than one hour.

Methylation of the enolic hydroxyl group of kojic acid (I) by the method of Campbell⁷ furnished (II), which on selenium dioxide oxidation in refluxing xylene for 30 minutes furnished the methyl ether (V) in 68-72% yields.

Comenaldehyde Methyl Ether (2-Formyl-5-methoxy-4H-pyran-4-one) (V).—A mixture of 2-(hydroxymethyl)-5-methoxy-4*H*-pyran-4-one⁷ (2.8 g.) and selenium dioxide (2.4 g.) in dry xylene (100 ml) was refluxed, using a water-separator, for 1/2 hr. The solution was concentrated to half its original volume and decanted from the solid residue. The crystals, which immediately separated were redissolved by heating and the solution was allowed to cool slowly at room temperature. The aldehyde, crystallising in ¹/₂ inch needles, was collected and washed with ether, m.p. 198-200°, yield 2.0 g. (72%). It was purified by crystallisation from glacial acetic acid in faint yellow needles, m.p. 203°. A sample, sublimed at ordinary pressure, yielded the analytical specimen as long white needles, m.p. 206° (lit.⁴ m.p. 205-206°). (Found: C, 54.31; H, 4.0. Calc. for C₇H₈O₃: C, 54.54; H, 3.90%). *Thiosemicarbazone derivative* melted at 245° (lit.⁴ m.p. 244.5-46°). (Found: C, 41.91; H, 4.2. Calc. for C₈H₉O₃N₃S: C, 42.29; H, 4.0%).

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